

Tewa Pueblo Religion

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This entry discusses religious ideas and practices of the six currently inhabited Tewa-speaking Pueblos of northern New Mexico, USA. The time span covered is roughly from the mid-20th century, when several major ethnographic works were published, to the present. Most of the details presented are based on the personal experiences of the author. At the time of this writing, Tewa religion is a syncretic assemblage of Indigenous and Spanish-introduced elements. Religious practices are largely compartmentalized into Indigenous and Catholic components, and community members are well aware of which is which. Some Spanish Catholic elements have been incorporated into Indigenous practices, and vice versa, but the two forms of practice basically co-exist side by side. Over the past century the Tewa population has grown substantially, and the dominant society has come to appreciate and support Indigenous religious and cultural practices to a much greater extent. Over the period of my own observation (1994 to 2024) there has been notable revitalization in Indigenous practice, and a decrease in Catholic practice. However, it is still typical for life-cycle rituals to involve both Indigenous and Spanish components which are performed by Tewa religious society leaders and Catholic priests, respectively. Ancestral (archaeological) sites with traditional Tewa names are found across a much broader area of northern New Mexico often referred to as the Tewa Basin, ranging from the towns of Abiquiu, El Rito and Ojo Caliente in the north to Los Alamos and White Rock in the West, Santa Fe in the south, and Cordova and Velarde in the east. Settlements in these broader areas were largely vacated during the 16th and 17th centuries as a consequence of Spanish colonialism. Most of the present-day tribal lands of the six communities into which this broader population coalesced were established through Spanish land grants in the late 17th century. The Indigenous religious components discussed in this entry, minus obvious Spanish introductions (e.g. allusions to the wheat-growing power of ancestral cloud beings), likely characterized ancestral (pre-contact) Tewa communities of these areas, although some dances (e.g., the Comanche Dance) must have originated more recently. Tewa oral traditions suggest the ancestors of Tewa people lived to the northwest of the Tewa Basin, and that Tewa society originated through the coming together of two distinct peoples (the winter and summer people) who migrated into the Tewa Basin from this northern homeland at different times (winter came first, and summer followed). Archaeological and bio-archaeological evidence reinforce this view and identify the northern drainages of the San Juan River in southwest Colorado, USA, as the most likely ancestral homeland. In addition, connections between etymological analyses of Tewa vocabulary and archaeological material culture suggest the Tewa language originated as a distinct language in the vicinity of what is today known as the Montezuma Valley in southwest Colorado. Taken together, the evidence suggests the Tewa language and most of the ancestral Tewa population migrated from this northern homeland into the Tewa Basin in the late 13th century. However, Tewa oral tradition and archaeological evidence suggest a significant socioreligious reformation accompanied this migration. So, while contemporary religious ideas, and some contemporary practices, originated in the northern homeland of Tewa ancestors, other contemporary practices likely originated in the Tewa Basin.

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Tewa Basin

Region tags: Northern New Mexico, United States of America, North America

Area of Spanish land grants to Tewa villages in the

18th century.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ortiz, Alfonso (1969) *The Tewa World: Space, Time, Being and Becoming in a Pueblo Society*. University of Chicago Press.
- Source 2: Sweet, Jill D. (2004) *Dances of the Tewa Pueblo Indians: Expressions of New Life*. School of American Research Press, Santa Fe.
- Source 3: Laski, Vera (1959) *Seeking Life*. American Folklore Society, Philadelphia.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1920 CE - 2020 CE

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Keresan-speaking Pueblo villages are to the immediate south and Tiwa-speaking Pueblo villages to the immediate north. There is also a Tewa-speaking village on Hopi First Mesa in Arizona, and Catholicism has been present since the 1600s.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: In earlier centuries Franciscan missionaries sought to undermine Tewa religion, but this is no longer the case. This being said, community members often view traditional Tewa religion as being in competition with other, non-Indigenous religions today.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Tewa religion was discriminated against in various ways from 1600 through passage of the American Indian Religious Freedom Act in 1978.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: Tewa religion is no longer discriminated against, although the dominant surrounding society exerts inherent pressure with regard to cultural continuity.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Group-level warfare is not present, although crime and discrimination based on ethnic identity certainly is.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: In previous centuries Tewa people did have violent conflicts with Spanish and Comanche people, but organized violent conflict has not occurred since pacification of the Comanche in 1875.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– No

Notes: It is very rare for a non-Indigenous individual who does not have a Tewa relative to be initiated into any Tewa religious society, although Indigenous people from other tribes can be initiated based on friendship ties.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Differences in prestige are based on initiation and accomplishment and are not assigned at birth. The "society men" are sometimes referred to as a group, but these are not social classes in the common understanding.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

Notes: There are multiple initiation rites that an individual passes through in the process of becoming seh'ta "ground and stewed" or "cooked".

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

Notes: Most religious societies have only male membership, and a few have only female membership. Although both men and women have ceremonial roles, only the summer people and winter people are mixed gender.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Members of religious societies are chosen by existing members and must go through an initiation process as part of joining. There are additional initiations for the officers of these societies.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– I don't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Tewa religion does not seek conversions, although religious societies do actively recruit members from the community.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: In Tewa villages there is an elected secular government, established during the era of Spanish colonization, but this government is viewed as separate from the "traditional" religious societies and leadership which is the focus of this entry.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There is no official religious canon, although knowledgeable elders and leaders have a clear idea of how rituals and practices should take place. Individuals can be excommunicated from the community for certain offenses against the traditional religion.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Physical punishment, such as lashing, appears to have been practiced at the beginning of the period in question, but whether this continues to the present is unknown.

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– No

Notes: I am not aware of explicit punishment by spiritual beings, but community members do talk about something like karma being a vehicle for punishment for transgressions.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 2000

Notes: Estimated population of the six named Tewa villages in the 1940 census.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 10

Notes: Based on the population of Rio Arriba County, New Mexico, in the 1940 census.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Notes: Tewa Pueblo religion is closely related to those of other Pueblo communities where different languages are spoken.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: The Hunt Chief is the traditional apical religious leader, although this office is unoccupied in several villages today.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

Notes: Tewa religion is organized primarily at the village level, but today members of

religious societies often serve in other villages as needed.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

Notes: Each religious society has an independent chapter in each village, but individuals initiated into specific societies often serve in the chapters of other villages.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 4

Notes: The hunt society is at the top of the traditional hierarchy, followed by the Summer and Winter moiety leaders, then the other religious societies of paatowa "made people," and finally the seht'a towa "dry food people", the common members of the pueblo.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Traditional religious leaders are believed to have the ability to communicate and intercede with ancestral people and other spirit beings.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural powers are acquired through a combination of innate abilities, training, initiation, and practice.

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Some traditional leaders report being chosen through visions or dreams involving ancestors, or interactions with an animal spirit-being.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

Notes: Training and initiation processes involve the transmission of supernatural abilities from elders to trainees/initiates.

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: The selection process for training and initiation into religious societies involves observation of specific personality traits and abilities in individual community members.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: Leaders of Tewa religious societies are recruited by the current membership for training and initiation into the society. While there are network effects in this process, recruitment is not hereditary.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Notes: Formally, successors are selected by the current membership of a society rather than its leader, but in practice leaders may exert influence on such decisions, as they seem to derive from consensus-based decision-making.

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: Successors for leadership positions are selected by consensus of the existing membership of a religious society.

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Notes: The secular elected government of a Tewa village operates independently of the traditional religious leadership, which today is primarily responsible for organizing and leading ceremonial and life-cycle rituals. Prior to European colonization the religious society hierarchy was the only form of government.

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

Notes: The dry food people are not involved in choosing religious society leaders.

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: Prayer is a part of the process by which existing religious society members choose new leaders.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: Tewa traditional religion is primarily oral, although it has material manifestations in the form of dance, regalia, buildings and shrines.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: There is religious architecture in the form of te'e "special houses" or kivas, nansipu "earth navels" or shrines, both are humble in appearance rather than monumental. The most monumental aspects of Tewa built environments are the b'uupingeh "bowl-middle-heart-places" or plazas in which public mass dances occur.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: These are located around the periphery of the Pueblo.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The kiva is the closest thing to a temple in a Tewa village. These can be large enough to accommodate large groups of dancers, but they are not exactly monumental.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Temporary altars are set up within kivas during specific ceremonies, and permanent collections of stones in the plaza (nankwiyo nansipu pingeh 'earth mother earth navel middle place') serve as locations for propitiation and prayer at other times.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Plazas

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Only religious public space

Notes: Imagery related to key concepts of clouds, rain, growth, and abundance occur in many contexts, although often such expressions are subtle and muted. Such imagery is incorporated into woven garments worn as ceremonial regalia, altars erected in kivas, temporary structures housing the patron saint of the pueblo on feast days, and in the terraced form of the rooflines of kivas. Elements of ceremonial regalia are also often displayed on walls in the home. And imagery related to key religious concepts is typical of painted pottery decoration.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Awanyu, a horned water serpent, is a common iconographic element.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Clouds and mountains are viewed as animate and are depicted in iconography

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Oxua (cloud-beings) are ancestral rain spirits, called kachinas in other pueblos, which are depicted in masked anthropomorphic form in art. In some pueblos initiates learn how to take in the spirit of one of these beings through masked dancing. This does not occur in public contexts in Tewa religion today, but it may have in the past, and it may still occur entirely in secret within the kiva today.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: In older iconography cloud beings are represented as terraces with eyes. Today, terraces continue to have this connotation but do not include facial features.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Tewa religion conceives of a spirit world as a consubstantial counterpart to the physical world, but one where time is collapsed. So, the world of the ancestral spirits is also the world that departed souls enter. Historical mural paintings uncovered through archaeology depict this idealized spirit world of harmony and abundance.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: Corn meal bowls with four terraces around the rim are used to represent the earth, with the pueblo in the center. Terracing is also associated with kiva architecture, indicating the role of the kiva as a lake-place, or a place where one can pass between the physical and spiritual worlds.

↳ Humans:

– No

Notes: Oxua are depicted in art but are considered to be anthropomorphic ancestral rain beings rather than living human beings.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Although all of creation is endowed with sacredness, there are blessing places on the tops of cardinal hills and mountains, and at specific caves and springs, that are dedicated to prayer and other forms of religious practice. These locations are known to Tewa religious specialists but are not openly shared with outsiders.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Religious society members make seasonal pilgrimages to a variety of locations to gather necessary materials for ceremonies. It is likely that in the past society members also made pilgrimages to specific sacred locations to pray and leave offerings.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Animate spirit is envisioned as inhabiting a body, and of being released from it in death. A death ritual that illustrates this distinction is the practice of carrying food outdoors in a bowl and breaking it outside, so that the spirit of the deceased will begin its journey and not linger with the body. The same concept underlies masked kachina ceremonialism.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit of initiated community members travels to the mountains to join with other clouds upon death. Religious specialists report experiences communicating with ancestral people in dreams, although such communication does not appear to involve communication with specific named individuals who were known while they were alive.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: In archaeological sites it appears that children who died very young were often buried beneath the floors of houses, perhaps indicating a belief in reincarnation of infants. Fully-initiated adults are most often described as going back to the lake of emergence and going back into the spirit world at death.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Notes: Grave goods do occur in archaeological burials; whether this practice continues today is unknown to me.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Cemeteries are notable around the periphery of a village today, and in the past adults and elders were most often interred in community ash piles or middens located around the periphery of the village.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: In archaeological sites, infants and small children are often buried beneath house floors.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: The ancestral rain beings are generally viewed as looking down on the people to monitor their behavior and hearts, but this is a class of being, not a single supreme being.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: They can be seen with one's waking eyes in the form of clouds, and they can be seen as humans in dreams.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Notes: There is a concept that people can sometimes keep their true intentions hidden from the ancestral rain beings, although this is judged as a character flaw.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: This is especially true during dances when people gather in plazas.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– No

↳ Human spirits can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Notes: When spirits communicate with the living, they generally invite them to do something.

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Ancestral rain spirits signal their approval of the human community by bringing rain.

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Ancestral rain spirits signal their disapproval of the human community by withholding rain.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– No

Notes: As far as I can ascertain, human spirits dwell in their own time in the spirit world, they do not dwell in the present and remember their time in the physical world.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The emotions of the ancestral rain spirits are driven by their perceptions of the human community and are revealed through the weather.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The emotions of the ancestral rain spirits are driven by their perceptions of the human community and are revealed through the weather.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

- ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: The answers below relate to Awanyu, a horned water serpent spirit of flowing water and lightning.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Awanyu has knowledge of water, streams, and precipitation.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– No

Notes: Awanyu can bring live-giving water or destructive floods, but these seem to occur independently of human behavior.

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– No

Notes: Awanyu can bring live-giving water or destructive floods, but these seem to occur independently of human behavior.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No
Notes: Awanyu is inherent in flowing water and does not necessarily cause it.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes
Notes: There are many different types of Oxua (cloud beings) and Awanyus (water serpents).

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:
– I don't know
Notes: There are indications of hierarchy among kachinas in other pueblos. I do not have any information on this with regard to Tewa Oxua.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
– Yes
Notes: There are many different types of Oxua which refer to different types of being and forces of nature.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:
– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: The community is awarded/punished collectively through the weather.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

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- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - No

- ↳ Other [specify]
- No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

- No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

- Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

- No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

- No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

- Yes

- ↳ Monogamy (males):
 - No

- ↳ Monogamy (females):
 - No

- ↳ Other sexual constraints (males):
 - Yes
 - Notes: During ritual preparation.

- ↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Fasting is a part of certain ceremonies for certain individuals, but it is not required for membership.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: There are references in literature to former child sacrifice, but I have never heard it discussed.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Members are generally expected to feed visitors during dances and to contribute to giveaways. Cornmeal is a substance typically offered in prayers.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Members are generally expected to take part in ceremonies, to dance and to attend practices. Members are also expected to greet the sun each morning in prayer.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Notes: Rituals are a part of daily life but they are not extensive or time consuming as far as I can tell.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 500

Notes: Adults are generally expected to participate in dances, either as dancers or as part of the chorus or as observers.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 8

Notes: Public dances usually last an entire day, plus 4 evenings of practice beforehand.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Religious specialists inspect regalia of dancers and ensure dancers are dancing properly.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Dances generally involve mass formations that move in unison or in otherwise coordinated ways.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: I am not aware of past use of mind-altering substances by dancers, and intoxicants are not a part of public ceremonies today.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: As far as I am aware, everything associated with public dances is considered part of an overall prayer for abundance.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: Co-religionists are generally referred to as brothers and sisters, and religious leaders are referred to as uncles, fathers and mothers.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Food is redistributed during ceremonies, and families are expected to feed community members in need during feasts.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Community members can receive food aid through US social safety net programs.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Goods are also redistributed during ceremonies to all in attendance, including outsiders.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Community members can receive poverty relief through US social safety net programs.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Elder care occurs primarily within the family.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Elder care occurs primarily through the family.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: There is formal religious instruction as part of initiation processes into religious societies.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Young people in Tewa villages today can attend public schools.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Each religious society has an internal hierarchy, and the societies themselves are also bureaucratic, each with its own functions and responsibilities.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Tewa villages have elected governments which interact with the US Government on a government to government basis.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: The leaders of the summer and winter moieties are responsible for organizing periodic community ditch cleaning events, and they also maintain the ditch works.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: I believe other tribal organizations also contribute to management of the irrigation systems today.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Roads are built and maintained by tribal, county, state, and federal US governments.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: In the past, community members worked religious leaders' fields on their behalf. Community members are also expected to contribute to giveaways, although this is not required.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Tribal members pay US income tax.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: The tribe maintains its own police force. Although this is not exactly a police force, the Kosa or clown society enforces community norms through public ridicule of misbehaving individuals.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Tribal members interact with Federal police when capital crimes are involved.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: There is a tribal court.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Tribal members interact with US federal courts when appropriate.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Religious leaders can excommunicate community members who commit offenses against community traditions.

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: The Kosa or clowns can ostracize individuals who are not behaving properly.

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– I don't know

Notes: Technically, houses and fields are controlled by the tribal government, such that these assets cannot be bought or sold. It appears that they can be passed down within a family, but in the absence of an heir who wants to utilize the resource, it will revert to the tribal government for reallocation. I do not know if this mechanism can be invoked as punishment however.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Notes: Capital punishment is not allowed in New Mexico today.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: Incarceration.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: Fines related to court settlements.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: The "Spanish" tribal government has a legal code, but the traditional religious government does not.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Tribal members are US citizens and are subject to US law.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: There is a traditional war and scalp society within a Tewa village that formerly regulated and managed external conflict involving warriors. These societies have reduced functions today.

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Tribal members can enlist in the US military and there is a traditional of military service.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The United States is protected by the US military.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Although the Tewa language can be written today, most tribal members know Tewa as a spoken language.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Tribal members learn to read and write in English in school, and some learn to write Tewa as well.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Tribal members learn English due to being within US society.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: There is an annual round of ceremonial activities whose dates have become increasingly fixed,

but in the past these were based on seasonal indicators rather than a formal calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Tewa villages follow the standard US calendar for work schedules and public holidays.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The traditional economy, which held sway until the mid-20th century, involved subsistence agriculture with maize, beans, squash, chile, wheat, melons, and fruits; herding of sheep and cattle; and seasonal hunting and wild plant food gathering.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Today, most food is obtained through the cash economy, with limited production of maize and other traditional crops for food and ceremonial use.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Today, most food is obtained through the cash economy.

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